

Lahore High Court Refuses To Declare Underage Marriage as “Rape”

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Abstract:

This paper critically reviews a recent judgment by the Lahore High Court on underage marriages in Pakistan. It highlights an anomaly in the court's reasoning: although the petitioner argued that underage marriage constitutes statutory rape under Section 375 of the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC), the court focused instead on the validity of the marriage rather than the core issue of statutory rape. As per legal principles, the validity of a marriage falls under a different domain of Islamic law. This research advocates for nuanced legal interpretations and evidence-based decision-making when addressing sensitive issues like underage marriage in Pakistan.

Keywords: Underage Marriage, Rape, Criminal Law, Islamic Law

Introduction

In Writ Petition No. 57371 of 2023, filed in the Lahore High Court (LHC) in the case of *Nazar Muhammad v. DPO et al.*, the petitioner sought the recovery of his daughter, Mst. Yasmin, from the alleged illegal custody of the respondent. The LHC dismissed the petition, refusing to declare that the respondent was guilty of rape.

The petitioner contended that his daughter was 13/14 years old at the time of her marriage and, therefore, not legally competent to enter into a marriage contract. However, in her statement before the Magistrate, Yasmin claimed that she was 19 years old.

The LHC observed that it has long been established that when a girl marries after attaining puberty, the marriage cannot be considered “void” even if she has not reached the minimum legal age prescribed by law. Regarding the age of puberty, the LHC referred to *Yousuf Masih alias Bagga Masih*, which states¹

“...All the original texts of Hanafi jurisprudence are unanimous on the point that 9 years is the minimum age on which the declaration of a girl about her puberty can

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¹ *Yousuf Masih alias Bagga Masih and another v The State* [1994] SCMR 2102.

be accepted. For example Allama Shami, the well known Hanafi jurist, writes in his Radd-ul-Muhtar, volume 5,--- page 107.... And the minimum age of puberty for a boy is 12 years and for a girl is 9 years.

The petitioner's counsel argued that the respondent had committed rape under Section 376 of the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC), asserting that since Yasmin was a minor, her consent to marriage and consummation was irrelevant because Section 375 PPC defines any sexual act with a girl under sixteen years of age as rape, regardless of her consent. However, the LHC dismissed this argument, stating that the petitioner's counsel based his contention on a flawed assumption.

The LHC further asserted that the sexual offense described in Section 375 PPC cannot be equated with the consensual consummation of marriage with a legally wedded girl who has attained puberty, even if she has not reached the minimum age specified under the Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929. The Act provides punishment for marrying a girl under 16 years old, but does not declare such marriages void. The legality or illegality of a marriage, according to the LHC, must be adjudicated in light of Islamic injunctions.

Summary of the Judgment:

- a) A girl's marriage after attaining puberty, even without meeting the minimum legal age, cannot be considered void.
- b) Engaging in a sexual act with a girl under 16 years of age does not constitute rape if she is legally wedded, regardless of her consent.
- c) The sexual offense described in Section 375 PPC cannot be equated with the consensual consummation of marriage with a legally wedded girl who has reached puberty.

Discussion

On Point (a):

The petition aimed to declare the respondent's actions as a criminal offense, specifically rape, punishable under the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC), rather than to assess the validity of the marriage. However, the LHC's observations began by considering the validity of the marriage,

i.e., whether it was a “void marriage.” The court did not discuss what constitutes a void marriage under Islamic law, but noted:

"Furthermore, I could not find any precedent set by the Federal Shariat Court declaring a marriage void when a minor girl, without attaining the minimum legal age prescribed by law, contracted marriage after attaining puberty."

The LHC seemed to imply that a marriage could be declared void if solemnized before the legal age prescribed by law. However, this interpretation introduces a novel dimension to the issue and appears to depart from established principles. The study identifies the following conditions that could render a marriage void:

1. Marriage falls under the prohibited degrees of relationship, i.e., marriage between the parties having blood relations.²
2. Marriage prohibited by the reason of affinity (e.g., sister, aunt, niece, etc.)³
3. Marriage with a foster mother or a foster sister. The exception in case of fosterage is observed by Sunnis, where marriage is valid with a sister's foster mother, or foster sister's mother, foster son's sister, or foster-brother's sister.⁴
4. Marrying a woman who is undergoing Iddat is also void under Shia law.⁵
5. Marriage with someone else's wife, provided her marriage is still subsisting.⁶
6. Marriage of a Muslim women to a person from a different religion.⁷
7. Marriage with a fifth wife.⁸
8. Remarrying one's own divorced wife if a legal bar exists (under Shia Law).⁹

² 'Classification of Marriage Under Muslim Law', *Drishiti Judiciary* (Web Page) <<https://www.drishtijudiciary.com/to-the-point/ttp-muslim-law/classification-of-marriage-under-muslim-law>>.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ 'Void Marriage under Sharia Law - an Analysis with Special Reference to a UAE Case', *Lawyers in Dubai | Legal Consultants in Dubai* (Web Page) <<https://hhslawyers.com/case-study/void-marriage-sharia-law-analysis-special-reference-uae-case/>>.

⁸ Aishwarya Agrawal, 'Types of Muslim Marriage', *LawBhoomi* (Web Page, 1 May 2023) <<https://lawbhoomi.com/types-of-muslim-marriage/>>.

9. Marriage in violation of absolute incapacity (under Shia Law).¹⁰
10. Marriage during pilgrimage (under Shia law).¹¹
11. Marriage with any non-Muslim (under Shia law)¹²

Sir Dinshah Fardunji Mulla's *Principles of Mahomedan Law*—a frequently cited text on Muslim personal law in Pakistan,¹³ describes the following marriages to be void;

204A. Distinction between void (batil) and invalid (fasid) marriages.

a) (1)

a) (2) A void marriage is one which is unlawful in itself, the prohibition against the marriage being perpetual and absolute. Thus a marriage with a woman prohibited by reason of consanguinity....., affinity....., or fosterage.....is void, the prohibition against marriage with such a woman being perpetual and absolute.....¹⁴

Given that the case does not involve consanguinity, affinity, or fosterage, and there is no age-related condition among the enumerated causes of void marriages, it is safe to conclude that the LHC's focus on the validity of marriage based on age was misplaced. The court's reasoning may be termed as *ratio decidendi non sequitur*, as it does not follow logically from the facts of the case.

On point (b)

To address this point, it is essential to examine Section 375 of the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC), which defines rape as follows:

⁹ LAWNN.COM, 'Classification of Marriage under Muslim Law- Valid, Void & Muta Marriage' (Web Page, 2 April 2017) <<https://www.lawnn.com/classification-of-marriage/>>.

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Dr. Shahbaz Ahmad Cheema, 'Mulla's Principles of Mahomedan Law in Pakistani Courts: Undoing/Unraveling the Colonial Enterprise?', *Shaikh Ahmad Hassan School of Law* (Web Page)<<https://sahsol.lums.edu.pk/node/12831>>.

¹⁴ DINSHAH FARDUNJI MULLA, *Principles of Mahomedan Law* (N. M. Tripathi & Co., 7th ed, 1922) <<https://tile.loc.gov/storage-services/service/ll/llscd/23014769/23014769.pdf>>.

Rape. __ A person A is said to commit “rape” if A __

(a) penetrates his penis, to any extent, into the vagina, mouth, urethra or anus of another person B or makes B to do so with A or any other person; or

(b) inserts, to any extent, any object or a part of the body, not being the penis, into the vagina, the urethra or anus of B or makes B to do so with A or any other person; or

(c) manipulates any part of the body of B so as to cause penetration into the vagina, urethra, anus or any part of body of B or makes B to do so with A or any other person; or

(d) applies his mouth to the vagina, anus, urethra or penis of B or makes B to do so with A or any other person, under the circumstances falling under any of the following seven descriptions,

firstly, against B’s will;

secondly, without B’s consent;

thirdly, with B’s consent, which has been obtained by putting B or any person in whom B is interested, in fear of death or of hurt;

fourthly, with B’s consent, when A knows that A is not B’s husband and that B’s consent is given because B believes that A is another man to whom B is or believes herself to be lawfully married;

fifthly, with B’s consent when at the time of giving such consent, by reason of un-soundness of mind or intoxication or the administration by A personally or through another of any stupefying or un-wholesome substance, B is unable to understand the nature and consequences of that to which B gives consent;

sixthly, with or without B’s consent, when B is **under sixteen years of age**; or

seventhly, when B is unable to communicate consent.¹⁵

¹⁵ ‘Pakistan Penal Code’

<<https://pakistancode.gov.pk/pdf/files/administrator/d5622ea3f15bfa00b17d2cf7770a8434.pdf>>.

The *sixth description*, which applies to individuals under sixteen years of age, clearly sets the minimum age requirement for sexual acts under Section 375 PPC. Therefore, the LHC's assertion that the petitioner's counsel's argument was based on incorrect assumptions is open to challenge.

On point (c)

To determine whether the girl was legally wedded, it is necessary to review the laws of Pakistan governing Muslim marriages. The Muslim Family Laws Ordinance, 1961, is relevant, but it does not specify a minimum age for marriage. The applicable law in this context is The Child Marriage Restraint Act 1929¹⁶, section 4 of this Act, as promulgated in the province of Punjab, prescribes the following punishment for marrying a child.

Punishment for marrying a child.— If a person, not being a minor, contracts child marriage, he shall be liable to punishment of simple imprisonment which may extend to six months and fine of fifty thousand rupees.¹⁷

And section 2(a) of the aforesaid Act defines a Child as

"child" means a person who, if a male, is under eighteen years of age, and if a female, is under sixteen years of age;¹⁸

It is evident that Pakistani law establishes a legal age for marriage. However, the judgment does not indicate whether any medical evidence was presented to determine the girl's age, aside from her own statement. In the absence of compelling evidence, how can the court safely conclude that the girl was legally wedded?

Conclusion

Based on the discussion, it is clear that the case does not involve consanguinity, affinity, or fosterage. Therefore, the LHC's focus on the sanctity of marriage, whether void or not, is irrelevant as it falls outside the petition's subject matter.

¹⁶ 'Child Marriage', *UNFPA Pakistan* <<https://pakistan.unfpa.org/en/topics/child-marriage-4>>.

¹⁷ 'The Child Marriage Restraint Act 1929' <<http://punjablaws.gov.pk/laws/147a.html>>.

¹⁸ *ibid*

Furthermore, Section 375 PPC clearly defines the sexual acts mentioned therein as rape if committed against anyone under sixteen years of age, regardless of consent. Additionally, the Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929 provides punishment for marrying a girl under sixteen. In light of these relevant laws, the LHC's assertions regarding the petitioner's counsel's assumptions merit detailed scrutiny.

Moreover, while Pakistani law establishes a legal age for marriage, the absence of medical evidence regarding the girl's age and the court's reliance solely on her statement raises questions about the certainty of her status as a *legally wedded girl*.

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